

MAIN DETERMINANTS OF DEMAND FOR DIGITAL SERVICES IN VITICULTURE

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ABSTRACT

Viticulture, like any economic sector, undergoes structural changes caused by changes in the business environment. From the era of the "green revolution", viticulture today develops in the framework of sustainable competitive development. Competitive development, which is based on new approaches to management and development of the economy. Today, sustainable competitive development of the industry is understood as this development that combines the principles of the circular economy and the use of bio-based technologies and products. Applying these principles requires tools such as internet connectivity, internet of things and digitization of business processes in viticulture. The aim of the present study is to identify the main determinants of the demand for digital services in viticulture. The main method used to identify these determinants is the questionnaire survey. Through a specially designed, tested and validated survey, information on the main determinants is collected.

KEYWORDS: digital services, viticulture, determinants

ABSTRAKT

Wie jeder Wirtschaftszweig unterliegt auch der Weinbau einem Strukturwandel, der durch Veränderungen im wirtschaftlichen Umfeld verursacht wird. Seit der "grünen Revolution" entwickelt sich der Weinbau heute im Rahmen einer nachhaltigen wettbewerbsfähigen Entwicklung. Eine wettbewerbsfähige Entwicklung, die auf neuen Ansätzen für das Management und die Entwicklung der Wirtschaft beruht. Unter nachhaltiger wettbewerbsfähiger Entwicklung des Sektors versteht man heute eine Entwicklung, die die Grundsätze der Kreislaufwirtschaft und den Einsatz biobasierter Technologien und Produkte kombiniert. Das Ziel der vorliegenden Studie ist es, die wichtigsten Determinanten für die Nachfrage nach digitalen Dienstleistungen im Weinbau zu ermitteln. Die wichtigste Methode zur Ermittlung dieser Determinanten ist die Fragebogenerhebung. Mittels einer speziell entwickelten, getesteten und validierten Umfrage werden Informationen über die wichtigsten Determinanten gesammelt.

STICHWORTE: digitale Dienstleistungen, Weinbau, Determinanten

RÉSUMÉ

La viticulture, comme tout secteur économique, subit des changements structurels dus à l'évolution de l'environnement des affaires. Depuis l'ère de la "révolution verte", la viticulture se développe aujourd'hui dans le cadre d'un développement compétitif durable. Un développement compétitif qui repose sur de nouvelles approches de la gestion et du développement de l'économie. Aujourd'hui, le développement compétitif durable de la filière s'entend comme ce développement qui combine les principes de l'économie circulaire et l'utilisation de technologies et de produits biosourcés. L'application de ces principes nécessite des outils tels que la connectivité internet, l'internet des objets et la

numérisation des processus commerciaux dans la viticulture. L'objectif de la présente étude est d'identifier les principaux déterminants de la demande de services numériques dans la viticulture. La principale méthode utilisée pour identifier ces déterminants est l'enquête par questionnaire. Une enquête spécialement conçue, testée et validée permet de recueillir des informations sur les principaux déterminants.

MOTS-CLÉS: services numériques, viticulture, déterminants

INTRODUCTION

Viticulture, like any economic sector, undergoes structural changes caused by changes in the business environment [Borisov and Garabedian, 2020]. From the era of the "green revolution", viticulture today develops in the framework of sustainable competitive development [Borisov, 2021]. Competitive development, which is based on new approaches to management and development of the economy. Today, sustainable competitive development of the industry is understood as this development that combines the principles of the circular economy and the use of bio-based technologies and products. Applying these principles requires tools such as internet connectivity, internet of things and digitization of business processes in viticulture [Fidanska, Borisov and Nikolov, 2021].

The aim of the present study is to identify the main determinants of the demand for digital services in viticulture. The main method used to identify these determinants is the questionnaire survey. Through a specially designed, tested and validated survey, information on the main determinants is collected.

Organization of a survey. In order to collect the necessary information, to calculate the above-mentioned indicators, the implementation of the following research activities is undertaken [Borisov and Radev (2020):

- preparation of a survey card to study the state and needs of wine farms regarding the digital services offered on the market;
- conducting a survey and focus groups from the viticulture sector in Bulgaria during the period March 4, 2022 - April 30, 2022;
- conducting a survey and organizing focus groups of wine farms in Plovdiv (03.04.2022-03.17.2022), Hisara (05.01.2022-05.14.2022) and Asenovgrad (05.14.2022-05.30.2022), Haskovo (01.06).2022-07.06.2022);
- processing of primary data from questionnaires and focus groups, as well as building a database (03.04-06.10.2020);
- performing an analysis of the strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats for the development of beekeeping farms in Bulgaria (11.06 – 15.06.2020);
- identification of the main needs for increasing the competitiveness of beekeeping farms in the future (15.07-18.07.2020);
- identification of the specific needs related to the restructuring of agricultural sectors, characterized by a large number of bee farms (15.08-20.08.2020).

The database of the Directorate "Development of Rural Areas" and the Directorate "Compensatory Measures" of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications - Sofia was used as a source for forming the sample. The resulting general population consists of 10,542 organizations that

meet the criteria defining them as MFA on the territory of the country. In forming the sample, the method of simple random sampling was used, and the constituent units were selected through non-returnable selection. The sample size is 31 surveyed bee farms.

District	Number	Survey period
Plovdiv	81	03/04/2022-03/17/2022
Hisara	20	01.05.2022-14.05.2022
Asenovgrad	35	14.05.2022-30.05.2022
Haskovo	61	01.06.2022-07.06.2022
Total:	197	
Focus group 1 (Plovdiv)	10	
Focus group 2 (Asenovgrad)	11	
Total:	218	

Figure1. Planned number of surveyed farms by region and focus group size. Source: Own.

The survey card includes 31 surveyed vineyards during the period 04.03.2022 - 07.06.2022. The study contains a synthetic amount of data needed to conduct an objective analysis of identifying the determinants of demand for digital services.

The survey card covers a total of 10 questions, structured to quickly determine the determinants of demand [adapted model of Borisov, Stoeva and Dirimanova,2021].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

On the Bulgarian market there are suppliers of various services and equipment as well as software for both partial and complete transition to digital management of the viticulture. In this part of the research, we aim to profile what the demand for digital services is on the part of the Bulgarian farmer, as well as to determine the benefits and obstacles of the introduction of digitalization as a tool for effective management of the viticulture.

The following questions included in the survey aim to collect information about the main determinants of the search for digital services by the owners, as well as to identify the main obstacles limiting access to these services.

Figure 2 shows the owners' answers to the question "What digital services do you use in your business?". The data from the conducted survey indicate that most often the owners use digital services of the type - "specialized in weather info services, navigation systems, specialized software", 63.4% of the total surveyed persons. In the second place, the owners indicate that they use digital services specialized in the management of technological processes, 24.2% of the total respondents indicated this type of service. In the last place, as a preferred digital service, the owners indicated the one that specializes in the management of managerial services, 12.4% of the total respondents.

Figure 2. Digital services used by owners. Source: survey data among 197 respondents, 2022.

The next question in the survey is "How do you rate the benefits of the digital services you use?". The purpose of the question is to collect information about the generated benefit from the use of digital services, when carrying out the daily activities of the farmer on his farm. Figure 13 shows the assessment of the benefits of using digital services in farm management. Owners rate the following benefits as most significant: (1) efficient management of the viticulture enterprise (average rating – 4.57); (2) improving positions in the food chain (mean score – 4.57) and (3) price information – mean score 4.57.

Figure 3. Assessing the benefits of using digital services. Source: survey data of 197 respondents, 2022. (1-5 scale used, with 1 being the weakest and 5 being the strongest)

The next question in the survey is "Where do you get information about digital services?". Figure 3 shows the percentage distribution of the answers received by the surveyed owners. From the data thus presented, it can be seen that the majority of owners learn about the offered digital services from the websites and platforms of the providers of these services – 35.3% of all respondents indicated this answer. The next most important source of information is the sales representatives of digital services - 19.8% of all surveyed owners recognize them as a reliable source of information. Another reliable source for obtaining information is the specialized media - 17.1% of surveyed owners trust them.

Figure 4. Preferred information sources about digital services offered on the market. Source: own survey, data among 197 respondents, 2022.

The next question included in the survey is "Where is the digital service provider located?". Figure 5 presents the information obtained from this question. From the information presented in this way, it can be seen that regional providers of digital services are used - 465 of the total surveyed owners indicate this answer.

Figure 5. Location of the digital service provider. Source: survey data among 197 respondents, 2022.

By including the following question in the survey, the aim is to obtain information about the obstacles limiting owners' access to digital services. In Figure 16, the information on the main barriers to the use of digital services is presented. From the graphical analysis of survey data shows that the main limiting factors are: (1) lack of experience in using digital services on the part of the owners - 23.5% indicated this factor as the most significant problem; (2) the high price of the offered service – 21.4% of all surveyed owners and (3) complexity of the digital service – 19.6% of the surveyed owners stated that they do not use this type of service due to its complex nature.

Figure 6. Barriers limiting access to digital services. Source: survey data among 197 respondents, 2022.

Another factor that was investigated in the conducted survey is the provision and sharing of access to the digital services offered in the sector. Figure 7 shows the distribution of the answers received by the surveyed owners.

Figure 7. Access to digital services. Source: survey data among 197 respondents, 2022.

From the data thus presented, it can be seen that the owners prefer to use digital services individually - 73.1% of the surveyed owners stated this. Next is the group of owners who use digital services on a subscription basis - 19.9% of all surveyed owners.

The next question in the survey is "Do you participate in specialized information events related to digital solutions?". The data from the responses obtained are presented in Figure 8. Of all surveyed owners, 50.9% stated that they participate in seminars and conferences dedicated to the issue.

Figure 8. Do you participate in specialized information events related to digital solutions (services).

Source: survey data among 197 respondents, 2022

CONCLUSIONS

- Digitization in the viticulture sector is in its infancy. Viticulture and wine enterprises have mainly managed to digitize their accounting and supply activities. They have partly managed to digitize some critical technological phases of the production process such as irrigation and monitoring of the vineyard, control and monitoring of the distillation process.
- The challenges associated with the application of precision agriculture in the industry can be divided into two broad areas: (1) those inherent in the technological means used in precision agriculture (drones, robots, GPS, etc.), raising questions of technological control, human safety, civil liability and privacy, and (2) those emerging alongside the development of precision agriculture as an autonomous technological field.

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